

Psychosomatic impact of indoor spaces on inhabitants: Factors affecting physical and mental health of senior citizens in the residential buildings

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ABSTRACT: Our built environment and immediate surroundings influence our lifestyle and health significantly as we spend most of the time indoors, almost everyday. A balanced linkage between the aesthetically sound indoor space design and healthy living has already begun to gather momentum, especially in the post-pandemic scenario and considering the rise in senior population. Increasing awareness and realization of the impact of indoor spaces on our physical and mental health, has channelized our attention towards wellness-oriented interior designs for senior citizens. However, such aspects are often overlooked in urbo-architectural styles that lay minimal emphasis on overall well-being of the inhabitants. This paper identifies the factors such as, color variations, presence of light, incorporation of Vastu Shastra and Feng-shui principles, provision of open and green spaces and few others; that need to be considered while designing indoor spaces for overall wellness. The methodology includes literature review and study of space planning, design features, material and finishes of the existing residential units. A survey within a community through a questionnaire and interaction with the residents highlights the factors that impact their physical health and mental state. These factors have been analyzed for their association with the overall comfort level of the residents through the 'Pearson's correlation' and the most critical aspect(s) has been identified.

Keywords: Adaptive Space Planning, Pandemic; Public spaces; Residential Interiors, Senior citizens, Urban Environment

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1. Introduction

The positive interaction between the building design and the psychology of the inhabitants plays a vital role in the development of a healthy built environment. According to Evans and Cohen (1987), an imbalance between the human behavior and environmental conditions can cause discomfort and lead to higher stress levels. Such situations become even more challenging for the senior inhabitants. Some of the recent studies emphasize on development of indoor spaces in line with the preferences and requirements of senior citizens, which also include incorporation and adaptation of various aspects in the existing spaces for making them senior-friendly (Mnea & Zairul, 2023). We spend a substantial amount of time indoors that influences our mental as well as physical health. Constant confinement within the indoor spaces becomes the determinant of our overall wellness and influences us psychologically and physiologically (Rice, 2019), especially for senior citizens. This necessitates greater level of harmonization of the Architectural and Interior designs,

and the mental health of the users. In such a scenario, the role of Architects and Interior designers becomes immensely significant in creating spaces that have a positive impact on the overall well-being of the users. With the dramatically rising senior population globally, world health has been a serious concern and requires sincere attention. More than 90 percent of the world population suffers from health issues which makes global ill-health a critical matter of concern (Lay, 2015; World Health Organization (WHO), 2017a). It is identified that one of the major causes of the ill-health is the lifestyle of an individual which includes overall routine and day-to-day activities. It is estimated that more than 60 percent of the illness are attributed to the lifestyle diseases, stress, environmental context and social circumstances (Public Health England, 2016). Our built environment plays a vital role in the determination of modern lifestyles which ultimately affects us mentally and physically. WHO (1946) defines health as not just the absence of a disease but, a state of overall well-being in terms of physical as well as mental wellness. With the changing trend of health diseases to lifestyle diseases, these can also be treated within the indoors by enhancing the spaces and surroundings which requires a unified approach (Bloom et.al, 2011 p.5)

Problem statement

With the rising count of senior population, there is a tremendous need for development of more residential spaces that are senior-friendly, to accommodate the rising numbers of inhabitants, especially the senior citizens in urban areas. Development of such spaces are often based upon incorporating attractive finishes. However, there is a need to design such spaces in accordance with, firstly, the human comfort, both physical and psychological; and secondly, by incorporating basic and necessary factors that influence senior citizens constantly while they are indoors; which is usually not emphasized upon and often gets neglected.

Significance of study

The dramatic rise in the urban senior population worldwide has drawn our attention towards need for quality spaces for a healthy living and overall well-being. Such spaces do not only require high-quality material and specification, but, need to be carefully designed by incorporating physical, social and psychological preferences of the inhabitants. Indoor spaces impact us in many ways, hence, the study of factors that influence the health of senior citizens, mentally as well as physically, is significant and makes this study inevitable.

Aim and objectives

The research aims at identifying the physical as well as psychological impact of the indoor spaces on the senior residents.

Objectives:

- To identify the factors of indoor space planning that contribute to the overall well-being of the senior residents
- To conduct a survey for identification of building design aspects that affect the senior citizens physically and psychologically.
- To statistically analyze the association of the identified factors with the overall comfort-level of the senior inhabitants.
- To identify the most critical factor that affects the physical and psychological state of senior citizens in the residential settings.

2. Urbanization and indoor living

Human living has always been strongly associated with nature and its components. Several recent researches have also showcased positive impact of natural environment on

the humans (Huang et. al, 2020; Martin et. al, 2020; Choe et. al, 2020). Nature influences us mentally and physically and contributes to a healthy living. However, over-urbanization and technological advancements have greatly created a barrier between the human living and nature. The building designs of the past encouraged integration of nature into the built environment which has diminished in the present times of modernized structures which have been designed as major energy consuming glass boxes with minimal openings. The occurrence of diseases and health related issues, particularly the ones linked with the indoor space design, is rising due to over urbanization and changing demographics. More than half of the world population is residing in the cities and it is estimated that another 2.5 billion count of population will be living in the urban areas by 2050 (United Nations. Department of International Economic, United Nations. Department for Economic, Social Information, Policy Analysis, & Social Affairs. Population Division, 2003). Matz et al (2015), indicates that the population shift from rural areas to urban environment plays a critical role in the overall health conditions of the residents as most of the urban senior population prefers to stay indoors. It is also observed that the proportion of the time spent indoors is rising even with the existing urban population. In the present scenario of digitalization and technological advancements, most of the senior citizens are confined to indoor spaces due to which they have limited social interaction which often inculcates negative thoughts with increased stress levels. Social isolation causes various health issues especially in the case of home-makers and senior citizens. The design of a space becomes a determinant of the health conditions and influences the inhabitants socially, psychologically and physically.

Impact of indoor spaces on the health of Senior citizens

Building design directly impacts comfort of senior inhabitants which ultimately, impacts their health, performance and productivity (Andargie, 2019; Shafaghat, 2015). The increasing concept of indoor living is a point of serious concern for the health of senior citizens. In one of the research, Samet and Spengler (2003), found a positive association between the times spent outdoors with the better health and improved well-being. Whereas, the times spent indoors was found to be negatively associated with the overall health and well-being. Tillmann et al (2018), further, indicates a strong positive association of open and green spaces with the social health, mental wellness and physical fitness. Malkin (1991), suggests various physical factors that need to be emphasized upon for creating a healthy space include, noise levels, quality of air, thermal comfort, color, texture, lighting, connection with nature and level of privacy. Prolonged indoor living can lead to sedentary lifestyle which ultimately affects the health of the inhabitants, making them prone to serious illness and eventually, mortality (Ackland et al, 2003). Poor indoor air quality can adversely impact our health and can lead to the risks of respiratory diseases (Fisk and Rosenfeld, 1997). According to Jones et al, (2019), indoor environment, if not developed and maintained correctly, can impact negatively on the physical as well as psychological health of the inhabitants, especially the senior residents. Furthermore, the trend of indoor living has negatively impacted the levels of sociability of an individual as most of the time is spent indoors either by choice or due to the hectic routine (Victor and Yang, 2012). Social isolation has been a critical factor that influences the health of an individual negatively, often leading to mental health issues in the senior age. Hence, the space design should be inviting that can encourage social interactions and enhance sociability of the residents. Sociopetal arrangement of spaces contribute to healthy living and active ageing by encouraging social inclusion which enhances the social, psychological as well as physical health of the residents. However, such aspects often get neglected while designing indoor spaces. The major emphasis is laid upon high-quality materials having higher aesthetic value to ensure higher Return on Investment (ROI), consequently, the social and psychological preferences of the senior inhabitants often get over-looked, resulting in the development of sociofugal spaces that adversely impact the sociability and ultimately impacts their social health negatively. A paradigm shift in the discipline of Architecture and

Interior design is inevitable for development of spaces with special consideration towards the social, physical and psychological preferences of the users. According to Barret et. al, (2015), the parameters associated with the overall comfort and satisfaction of the users mainly include the sound, light, temperature, daylight, air quality, color, level of complexity and flexibility. Other factors include personal control, ownership, ionization, solar gain, safety and security (Othman et. al, 2012).

Daylight

Daylight is often associated as a significant aspect of the healthy living environment, especially in the residential spaces which play a vital role for its inhabitants. Daylight has a tremendously positive impact on our mental and physical health. Exposure to sunlight allows the brain to release the serotonin, a hormone that is responsible for boosting the mood and focus. Amount of light is one of the determinants of health and influences us mentally and consequently, physically. A fair balance between the natural light and the artificial lighting can affect the inhabitants in several ways, from curing an illness to causing an illness, which becomes even more critical with the age. Some of the studies suggest that absence of daylight could be the cause for several health issues (Evans, 2003; Bower, 2005). It is also observed that Senior Citizens prefer to sit out in Sun in extreme winters and appreciate the connection with the nature, which indicates that the integrated development with convenient access to outdoors offers them sufficient daylight and boosts positivity and mental peace. It further enhances their sleep, reduce stress levels, enhances Vitamin D levels and brain functioning (Warner, 2017).

Noise

Frequent exposure to unwanted sound can have negative impact on our mental health, which ultimately affects physical health. Even a short-term exposure to undesirable noise leads to increased blood pressure (Jhariwala et. al, 2017), which gets worse incase of senior citizens and can lead to the risk of cardiovascular diseases. Prolonged exposure to noise can adversely affect the hearing ability to certain frequencies and may cause a permanent hearing damage in some cases, depending upon the age. According to another recent study by Auger et. al (2018), higher noise levels can seriously impact pregnant women, causing high blood pressure and possibly causing preeclampsia. Noise pollution can affect our mental health in several ways by often causing anxiety, sleeping disorder, emotional imbalance, aggression, hysteria etc. (Goines and Hagler, 2007).

Color

Colors can drive moods and actions of the inhabitants by impacting their feelings, and ultimately affecting them mentally and physically. Hence, their incorporation in the design need to be carried out wisely, especially in the case of residence design for senior citizens. One of the recent studies show that colors affect the energy of the space, mood, feelings and behavior of the inhabitants. However, most of the inhabitants are unaware of the effects of colors on their well-being. The preference is usually given to the ongoing trend and the psychosomatic impact of colors often gets neglected. (Hussain et. al, 2021). Another study by Jung et. al (2022) examined the psychological and physiological responses of the senior citizens towards various color schemes. The relationship between color preferences of senior citizens and depression was analyzed through Electroencephalogram (EEG) and Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS). Color is one of the vital components of an indoor space and a captivating tool that breaks the monotonous appearance. Colors have a significant influence on the inhabitants and becomes a driving force for the way the users behave and act. Sincere consideration and careful incorporation of the suitable color scheme can create a habitable and comfortable space for its users. However, it can also be responsible for inappropriate functioning of the space, if not done

correctly, as it impacts the moods, mental and physical health of the residents. Color preferences vary with the age and have varying impacts on health, gradually.

Texture

The interplay between the components of design and our psychological well-being is a continuous process. Varying textures can either energize greatly or become responsible for draining all the energy. Natural textures such as wood etc are often associated creating a feeling of warmth, however, use of metals often conjure an image of producing a feeling of coldness in a space. Incorporation of soft textures such as pillows, light curtains etc. bring in softness to overall indoor space which is soothing to the eyes unlike sharp corners and rigid forms and shapes. The scale of the textures should be in accordance with the overall space design, dimensions, openings, scale of furniture etc. Textures need to be incorporated in a unified manner and must be compatible with the rest of the components of design.

Air Quality

Indoor air quality is affected by various factors which include the material that is incorporated within the indoor space, our routine activities, and the surrounding air quality. Several studies (Lanthier-Veilleux, et. al, 2016), have also highlighted the health problems associated with dampness in the house. One of the recent studies by Scheepers et. al (2017) showcased that Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) that primarily originate from indoor sources such paints etc., are highly responsible for health-related issues such as nausea, headache, irritation in the eyes etc., having adverse effects on the health of senior citizens. Medgyesi et. al (2017) states that cooking stove etc., especially in the rural areas affects the pulmonary functions; whereas, Kurti et. al (2016) emphasized upon the respiratory issues caused due to exposure to Hazardous Air Pollutants (HAPs).

Furniture

Inappropriate furniture design can lead to various health issues, psychologically as well as physically. Sitting postures, especially for longer duration, can influence our physical health and ultimately, our mental health (Madan and Parashar, 2023). Studies have found an emotional connect between a particular furniture item and its user. Some people prefer to use a particular furniture, in a particular location and direction and at times, at a particular time of the day which brings them mental peace and satisfaction. Use of material for making furniture, its finishes, color also affect the mental health of users. Natural materials such as wood, bamboo are preferred against plastic, metals and other manufactured materials.

Temperature

Comfortable temperature in an indoor space could contribute substantially to the physical and mental well-being of the inhabitants (Altan et. al, 2015). Daylight influences thermal levels inside the building, hence, incorporation of daylight, in required and correct proportion, is essential (Anderson, 2015). Thermal comfort of an indoor space can enhance wellness, boost energy levels and motivates.

Nature

Nature plays a vital role in ensuring healthy living and active-ageing, enhances physiological as well as psychological health of humans. Outdoor spaces become an unavoidable aspect of the urban fabric that must be emphasized upon while designing spaces. Visual connection with the outdoors enhances memory, concentration and productivity which ultimately contributes greatly to psychological health which further improves the physical health (Ko et. al, 2020). An appropriate connect with nature acts as a healer, hence, integrating open and green spaces can bring mental peace and relaxation. Studies have shown positive effects of outdoor spaces, connection with the outside world

and natural environment on inhabitants. Views of the nature and outdoors uplift mood and productivity (Sharp et. al, 2014). Windows in the buildings act as a gateway between the inside and the outside world and form an appropriate connection between the inhabitants and the outside world, hence, become an essential part of the building design and must be emphasized upon.

3. Materials and Methods

The prime objective of this paper is to identify the factors that influence mental and physical health of the senior citizens in a residential built space, through literature review, which includes research papers, journals, online articles, books etc. The identified factors have been narrowed down through interaction with the senior inhabitants and the field experts such as Architects, Designers, Planners, Psychologists, Doctors etc. The identified factors have been statistically analyzed to understand their association with the overall comfort and satisfaction of the users through Chi-square test on SPSS, followed by the identification of the most critical one through Pearson's correlation.

4. Results

The research is conducted through a survey which includes senior residents of age 60 years and above. A total of 100 questionnaires were sent, out of which 84 respondents participated actively. Most of the respondents were within the age range of 61 to 70 years, followed by the age group of 71 to 80 years. Minimal responses were received from the seniors of age 80 years and above. 56.5 percent of the respondents are females and the rest are male users with around 76.7 percent of all the respondents staying in apartments.

The survey results consist of a wide range of responses due to broad classification of the residential spaces of the respondents which include rented or owned apartments, villas etc. which are usually mass-constructed by the builders and developers. Some of the respondents have got their spaces designed and developed incorporating the services of interior designers, vastu consultants, architects etc. The study provides mixed responses varying from respondents facing psychological challenges to absolutely satisfied respondents. Most of the respondents are the residents of rented accommodations such as pre-designed apartments. Since remodeling of these residential units is permitted upto a limited extent, the users incorporated slight changes in the design combined with incorporation of sustainable design and vastu principles to the possible extent. Some of these respondents underwent modifications such as knocking of a wall to open up a space for allowing more daylight and to ensure better air-flow inside, along with changing the colors of the walls as per the advice of experts. Another set of respondents incorporated indoor plants considering both, aesthetics and a way to connect with nature. It is observed that incorporation of plantation even in the smaller spaces such as balconies provided air quality space for mind relaxation, social interaction which contributed to wellness with reduced stress levels.

“Now, we have a better place to sit outside, relax and enjoy a cup of tea or read a book.” – says one of the respondents. In some of the cases the respondents reported a feeling of being claustrophobic, especially in the high-rise buildings. A sense of disconnect on the higher floors is reported by the inhabitants which resulted in social isolation leading to a feeling of loneliness, especially in the case of nuclear families where only one of the partners is working. “We live on the 20th floor of the building with our two sons who are working. There is a strong feeling of loneliness during most of the time of the day and a sense of disconnection with the outside world which makes us feel low.” – response from another respondent. “Vastu corrections in our house cleared up various obstacles which were, probably, the reasons for my anxiety issues” – reported by a respondent. Similar

responses from some more respondents indicate that there is a sense of depression among the inhabitants, especially in case of senior citizens; when the space they live in, is not favorable. On the contrary, some of the respondents reported healthy living conditions and active lifestyle. Availability of sufficient daylight and open space to perform activities like yoga, playing table-tennis etc. keeps them motivated. 18 respondents admitted that they have experienced minor to major improvements in their overall well-being, more motivated which enhanced their performance and productivity. Members of one of four families reported a substantial recovery over stress levels after moving to the new property that receives sufficient daylight as compared to the previous one. The survey reveals that Chi-square test on SPSS established the association between identified factors and overall comfort of the residents. The results have been described and the inferences have been drafted, based on the figure achieved, for acceptance or rejection of the hypothesis.

Ho: There is no significant association between the 'Identified factor' and 'Overall comfort' of Senior citizens

H1: There is a significant association between the 'Identified factor' and 'Overall comfort' of Senior citizens.

Association of Color with Overall comfort

Table I – Chi-square test for association between 'Color' and Overall comfort

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	21.234 ^a	12	.052
Likelihood Ratio	19.971	12	.059
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.155	1	.043
N of Valid Cases	84		

a. 13 cells (65.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

- 'Overall comfort' scores were correlated with 'Color', giving p-value greater than 0.05 which indicates that Ho has to be accepted i.e. there is no significant association between 'Color' and Overall comfort of the residents.

Association of Daylight with Overall comfort

Table II – Chi-square test for association between 'Daylight' and Overall comfort

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	39.841 ^a	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	42.557	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	31.786	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	84		

a. 14 cells (70.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .07.

- 'Overall comfort' scores were correlated with 'Daylight', giving p-value lesser than 0.05 which indicates that Ho has to be rejected i.e. there is a significant association between 'Daylight' and Overall comfort of the residents

Association of Nature with Overall comfort

Table III – Chi-square test for association between ‘Nature’ and Overall comfort

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	36.175 ^a	12	.001
Likelihood Ratio	42.201	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	26.978	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	84		

a. 14 cells (70.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .07.

- ‘Overall comfort’ scores were correlated with ‘Nature’, giving p-value lesser than 0.05 which indicates that Ho has to be rejected i.e. there is a significant association between ‘Nature’ and Overall comfort of the residents.

Association of Positive_energy_flow with Overall comfort

Table IV – Chi-square test for association between ‘Positive_energy_flow’ and Overall comfort

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	58.014 ^a	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	44.868	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	23.041	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	84		

a. 14 cells (70.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

- ‘Overall comfort’ scores were correlated with ‘Positive_energy_flow’, giving p-value lesser than 0.05 which indicates that Ho has to be rejected i.e. there is a significant association between ‘Positive_energy_flow’ and Overall comfort of the residents.

Association of Temperature with Overall comfort

Table V – Chi-square test for association between Temperature and Overall comfort

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	47.003 ^a	12	.055
Likelihood Ratio	24.237	12	.011
Linear-by-Linear Association	18.001	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	84		

a. 14 cells (70.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

- 'Overall comfort' scores were correlated with 'Temperature' scores, giving p-value greater than 0.05 which indicates that Ho has to be accepted i.e. there is no significant association between 'Temperature' and Overall comfort of the residents.

Association of Noise with Overall comfort

Table VI – Chi-square test for association between Noise and Overall comfort

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.985 ^a	9	.381
Likelihood Ratio	9.032	9	.368
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.324	1	.008
N of Valid Cases	84		

a. 9 cells (56.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .32.

- 'Overall comfort' scores were correlated with 'Noise', giving p-value greater than 0.05 which indicates that Ho has to be accepted i.e. there is no significant association between 'Noise' and Overall comfort of the residents.

Association of Air quality with Overall comfort

Table VII – Chi-square test for association between Air quality and Overall comfort

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	28.735 ^a	12	.005
Likelihood Ratio	24.224	12	.030
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.556	1	.008
N of Valid Cases	84		

a. 14 cells (70.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .11.

- 'Overall comfort' scores were correlated with 'Air quality', giving p-value lesser than 0.05 which indicates that Ho has to be rejected i.e. there is a significant association between 'Air quality' and Overall comfort of the residents.

Association of Texture with Overall comfort

Table VIII – Chi-square test for association between Texture and Overall comfort

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.752 ^a	12	.695
Likelihood Ratio	9.778	12	.656
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.779	1	.226
N of Valid Cases	84		

a. 14 cells (70.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .07.

- 'Overall comfort' scores were correlated with 'Texture', giving p-value greater than 0.05 which indicates that Ho has to be accepted i.e. there is no significant association between 'Texture' and Overall comfort of the residents.

Association of Furniture with Overall Satisfaction

Table IX – Chi-square test for association between Furniture and Overall satisfaction

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	20.554 ^a	12	.049
Likelihood Ratio	17.114	12	.112
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.336	1	.004
N of Valid Cases	84		

a. 16 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .11.

- Overall comfort scores were correlated with 'Furniture', giving p-value lesser than 0.05 which indicates that Ho has to be rejected i.e. there is a significant association between 'Furniture' and Overall comfort of the residents.

The survey results have been further tested with the Pearson's correlation on SPSS, for identification of critical factors, out of all the identified factors, that influence comfort level of the residents. As per the test results incorporation of daylight, with the value of 0.606**, significant at 0.01 level, has a substantial impact on the mental and physical health of the senior residents. The test results further indicate a substantial influence of nature, positive energy flow, quality of the indoor air in the indoor space design, with the values 0.580**, 0.559** and 0.459** respectively, significant at 0.01 level. It is observed that other factors such as Texture, Furniture, color and Temperature; have a relatively moderate impact on the mental health of the residents.

Table X – Pearson's correlation results

Correlations											
		Color	Daylight	Nature	Positive Energy flow	Air quality	Noise level	Temperature	Texture	Furniture	Overall Comfort
Overall Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.216 [*]	.606 ^{**}	.580 ^{**}	.559 ^{**}	.459 ^{**}	.293 ^{**}	.291 ^{**}	.135	.324 ^{**}	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.041	.000	.000	.000	.000	.007	.007	.220	.003	
	N	84	84	84	84	84	84	84	84	84	84
* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).											
** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).											

5. Conclusions

Domestic well-being is a basic requirement that contributes to the overall wellness of the senior residents and needs to be fulfilled for sound psychological and physical health. With the changing lifestyles, culture and demographics of the urban areas, it is necessary to adapt to the changing conditions and living trends which also influence the design of spaces that we live in. Mental and physical comfort cannot simply be achieved by borrowing or copying the décor from the past. It must accommodate itself to the modern trends, lifestyle and most importantly the needs of the residents, psychological, emotional as well as physical. Our built environment impacts the seniors significantly and plays a vital role in determining their health. In the urbo-architectural style which majorly focusses on vertical development, healthy indoor spaces are the major determinants of human health which impact mental and physical health of inhabitants which necessitates better harmonization of indoor spaces and human health. People living in the high-rise, often feel socially isolated and detached from nature. Connection with nature, direct or indirect, positively impacts the health of inhabitants and the same needs to be incorporated in the design, appropriately, for overall well-being. The study indicates that a healthy design also revolves around the flow of positive energy within the spaces which can either be achieved directly through design by incorporating natural elements or principles of vaastushastra or feng shui which connects the inhabitants to these elements and nature. It is observed that a large count of population is relying on the vastu corrections of their homes for overall well-being, comfort and satisfaction. Several high-rise buildings are being designed and developed on such principles that ensure a connection with nature, sufficient daylight and ventilation for all the floors. Mental conditions such as depression, which is commonly observed among people of the present world; can be taken care to a possible extent by developing age-friendly and health-friendly societal spaces.

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